

TRANSPORT TERMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH FORMED SEMANTICALLY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21102396>

Abstract: This article analyzes the issue of the formation of terms related to the transport sector. In particular, it discusses the semantic formation of terms related to the transport sector in Uzbek and English. In this regard, an analysis of theoretical data and the opinions of linguists in the field are presented and concluded. The terms in both languages, formed in a semantic way, are compared and analyzed using examples.

Keywords: *terminology, semantic method, meaning transfer, metaphor, transport terms, comparative analysis.*

Today, the field of terminology is one of the most relevant issues in linguistics. Since terms mainly appear in English, their comparative study with the Uzbek language is the focus of linguists. A number of areas have been analyzed by linguists, and in this article we will focus on the analysis of terms in the transport sector. There are several aspects in the study of terms, and in this article we will analyze the aspects of term formation, in particular, the semantic formation method of transport terms.

In Uzbek and English, transport terms undergo semantic changes, meaning transfer, breaking of connections between some meanings of polysemantic words, and the formation of new terms through the assimilation of some, that is, the semantic expansion of certain terms. This phenomenon is called “word formation by the semantic method” by O.S.Akhmedov. In some sources and research works, this method is also referred to as the “semantic-syntactic method” [Akhmedov 2020: 85].

The first ideas in Uzbek linguistics on the issue of term formation using the semantic method were noted by Professor S.Ibrohimov [Ibrohimov 1957: 63]. R.Doniyorov touched upon the scientist’s work in this area in his work “Some Issues of Technical Terminology of the Uzbek Language” and, showing the importance of the semantic method in the terminology of this area, emphasized that this method serves to enrich the terminology of the field. The scientist divided terms formed from common lexemes into several thematic groups [Doniyorov 1988: 76-79]. In addition, the use of this method in the process of term formation has been discussed to some extent in research conducted in some areas of Uzbek terminology. In particular, N.T.Khotamov in his work on literary terms [Khotamov 1971: 223], S.A.Azizov analyzed terms formed using the semantic method in some terms denoting the names of musical instruments and their parts of the Uzbek language [Azizov 1981: 284].

Yu.S.Stepanov emphasizes that the semantic development of a word is subordinated to the needs of two functions of the language: the assimilation of reality through metaphor and knowledge through scientific concepts, and notes that there are two directions in it. Firstly, there is an exchange of lexeme denotations, which is based on metaphor, and secondly, due to their inextricable connection with the system of word meanings, the meaning of the signified is constantly deepening [Stepanov 1976: 323]. Continuing his thought, the scientist emphasizes that a term arises as a result of the development of subsequent meanings of a word based on its own meaning.

Most linguists have emphasized that metaphor plays a key role in the formation of terms through the semantic method. Because new terms arise by taking certain features of common words: similarities in shape, color, and other aspects as a basis.

Let us consider the terms related to the field of transport in English and how they are expressed in Uzbek through the following examples.

“Gunner” – this term is mainly used in railway terminology and is expressed in Uzbek as ‘ko’rsatkich’ or ‘priborlar ko’rsatkichi”. This term is a military term in its original English meaning, i.e. ‘gunner, soldier with a gun’. The term is compared to the tip of a gun held by a soldier, and a transfer of meaning has occurred.

“Cripple track” – the English definition is “a short section of track or siding used for storing defective or disabled railcars or locomotives temporarily. This track allows railway operators to remove faulty equipment from the main line or yard tracks without disrupting other operations”. The first meaning of the word ‘Cripple’ is ‘a person who cannot use their arms or legs in a normal way’, and this term is used in the railway sector in metaphoric meaning. In Uzbek, it is expressed by the compound term ‘ta’mirlash yo’li’. The repair route is mainly used to repair damaged parts of wagons and locomotives.

“Bastard schooner” – ‘two-sailed Marseille schooner’. The English word ‘bastard’ means ‘unclean’ in Uzbek and is a swear word. Etymologically, this word in English has evolved over time from the meaning of ‘illegitimate child’ to anything that is not of a standard, pure nature. That is, this type of ship was expressed in the sense that it was different from traditional schooners, which caused this shift in meaning.

“Fish plate” – in general use means a fish bowl, but in the railway industry it is used as a term for a ‘connecting plate’. This is exactly what a piece of iron that connects rails is called.

“Frog” – “a component of a railway switch or turnout. Specifically, it is the part of the track where two rails intersect, allowing trains to cross over from one track to another”.

“Greyhound” – “a fast-moving ship or (tourist) bus”. While its original meaning in English meant a breed of dog, the meaning was transferred to the bus and ship based on the similarity in shape and speed characteristics. It is noteworthy that, on the one hand, there is a shift in meaning, and on the other hand, this term explains other terms in two branches of the transport sector.

“Lug” is a term that applies to almost all vehicles, and its definition in English is “a protruding part or handle on a piece of equipment or a structural component”. This term arose on the basis of a transfer of meaning in both languages. In Uzbek, this term is expressed as “quloqcha”.

“Dead ship” – ‘O’lik kema’ (a non-working ship). This term, which denotes biological inactivity, was formed as a result of a transfer of meaning in both languages, which are being compared.

It is noteworthy that in the languages being compared, we can observe that this phenomenon is more common in English. We have observed that terms formed through the transfer of meaning in English are usually expressed in Uzbek in a way that explains their meaning. Although the number of terms formed in this way in Uzbek is relatively small, they do exist. Although the semantic method is not as productive as other methods of term formation, we have examined its occurrence in the formation of transport terms in the languages being compared through examples.

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